

Activity Report of the 2024 Multidisciplinary Oncology-ENT Consultation Meeting in Eastern Algeria

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INTRODUCTION

The multidisciplinary consultation meeting (MCM) is a method for evaluating and improving professional practices. It brings together healthcare professionals from different disciplines. It is an opportune moment for sharing experiences and making decisions that provide cancer patients with the best possible care based on the current state of scientific knowledge.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This was a multicenter activity review for 2024 of the Onco-ENT Multidisciplinary Tumor Board (MTB) at the Annaba Cancer Center and surrounding provinces. The review included cases of primary cancers of the upper aerodigestive tract, localized cancers, or cancers with local and/or distant recurrence, which were reviewed for discussion or therapeutic validation.

RESULTS

A total of 22 MTBs were held, with an average frequency of 15 days. A total of 204 cases were reviewed (average number of cases per MTB: 9), with an average duration of 70 minutes. The average waiting time (diagnosis to MTB) was 7 days.

Regarding the presenting department: ENT: 39%, Oncology: 41%, Radiotherapy: 19%, Nuclear Medicine: 1%.

The reasons for submitting cases were: care planning in 28% of cases, post-surgical treatment decision in 39% of cases, diagnostic and staging accuracy in 17% of cases, change of treatment plan in 5% of cases, finalization of assessment in 15% of cases, follow-up information in 9% of cases, jejunostomy procedure in 4% of cases, and finally, request for expert opinion in 9% of cases.

The multidisciplinary team meeting (MDT) decision was made during the first MDT in the majority of cases (81%), while a second MDT was required in 19% of cases.

FOR THE MEDICAL ONCOLOGY SERVICE REPORT:

-Age and sex: the average age was 60 years (15-91) with a clear male predominance of 70%.

Figure No. 01: Distribution according to age and sex

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-Medical oncology services: 84 cases (41%) were referred to the various medical oncology services in the Eastern region:

Table No. 1: Distribution according to medical oncology service referral:

Medical department	Year 2024	Year 2023
Annaba	42=50%	30=77,5%
Guelma	13=15%	04=10%
Skikda	6=7%	02=01=5%
El Tarf	9=11%	01=01=2,5%
S/Ahras	7=8%	01=01=2,5%
Tebessa	5=6%	01=2,5%
Total	84= 100%	39=100%

Figure N°02: Distribution according to the medical oncology service. -Tumor location:

Figure N°03: Distribution according to tumor location.

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-Geriatric assessment:

Geriatric assessment (patients ≥ 70 years) was performed in 21 cases based on the G8 geriatric score and the Charlson Comorbidity Index. Thanks to this assessment, a modification of the oncological treatment was made in 30% of cases.-Chemotherapy indications:

Table No.02: Distribution according to therapeutic indication.

Year	Indication	CT Induction	CT Palliative	CT +/TARGETED THERAPY	Palliative Care
Year 2024		84	45 = 54%	34 = 40%	5 = 6%

- Outcomes of patients treated with CT:

Table No.03: Distribution according to patient outcome

Year	Patient Outcome	Radiotherapy Department	ENT Department	Oncology Department	
Year 2024		84	50 = 60%	23 = 18%	11 = 12%

Currently, we have observed complete remission in 48% of cases; stable disease in 32% of cases (during treatment); progression in 15% of cases; and death in 5% of cases.

CONCLUSION

Multidisciplinary care in ENT oncology is becoming an obvious necessity and represents the only guarantee of access to quality care. This activity report in RCP ONCO-ORL is reassuring but still leaves the parenthesis open in the direction of optimizing organizational aspects, of treatment start-up times.

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